

On the Output Conductance Dispersion due to Traps and Self-Heating in Large Bulk, FDSOI and FinFET nMOS Devices

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Self-heating (SH) important in scaled CMOS tech

✗ Degrades device **performance, reliability,** and overall **circuit functionality**
[S.E.Liu et al., IRPS 2014] [D.Jang et al., IEDM 2015]

➔ **It is crucial to evaluate experimental methods to monitor SH effects**
[S. S. Islam et al., TED 2004]

The **AC output conductance (g_{DD}) method** exploits the g_{DD} frequency dispersion to quantitatively characterize SHEs
[A. J. Scholten et al., IEDM 2009]

g_{DD} studies in different technologies

Previous studies on output conductance (g_{DD}) frequency dispersion:

- Bipolar transistors [M.Stoisiek et al., SSE 1980]
- III-V semiconductor devices
 - **Traps are known to cause g_{DD} frequency dispersion** [S.S.Islam et al., TED 2004] [J.M.Golio et al., TED 1990] [S.Choi et al., TED 1994]

Silicon-based devices are characterized by:

- Lower trap densities compared to III-V FETs
- **g_{DD} frequency dispersion is mostly attributed to SHEs** [B.M.Tenbroek et al., TED 1996] [P.Paliwoda et al., TDMR 2018]

Motivations of this work

We measured the g_{DD} frequency dispersion:

- Three CMOS technologies
- Applied V_{GS} range: [0.4; 1.0] V

Observations:

- We observe three V_{GS} ranges in which the g_{DD} exhibits a different frequency dispersion: **increasing**, **non-monothonic**, **decreasing**.

Are SHEs enough to explain g_{DD} f-dispersion?

Outline

1. Experimental and simulation setup
2. Explaining output conductance (g_{DD}) dispersion through SH
3. Explaining g_{DD} dispersion through SH and traps
4. Conclusions

Experimental setup

1. DC Measurements:

- I-V curves
- Temperature range: $[-25; 125] \text{ } ^\circ \text{C}$

2. RF Measurements:

- Calibration of the RF measurement setup
- Frequency range: $[10 \text{ kHz}; 10 \text{ GHz}]$
- Constant V_{DS}
- Gate voltage range: $[0.4; 1.0] \text{ V}$
- Averaging: 10
- De-embedding of parasitics down to M2

Simulation setup

1. TCAD Model:

- Metal structure up to M2 + lumped R_{th} for the wafer top and bottom
- Thermo-Drift-Diffusion model
- Mobility calibrated
- Reduced thermal conductivity in thin films
- Calibrated on a large set of DC and AC data

2. AC Simulations:

- Same as in RF measurements

3. Transient Simulations:

- Pulsed V_{GS} waveform at constant $V_{DS} = 1$ V

FinFET model calibration

High V_{DS} →

Low V_{DS} →

Excellent agreement is achieved!

g_{DD} f-dispersion in 3 FET architectures

$$g_{DD,n} = \frac{g_{DD}(f) - g_{DD,HF}}{g_{DD,HF}}$$

$g_{DD,HF}$ is computed at f_{HF} , which is largely independent of the chosen V_{GS}

g_{DD} dependence on the applied V_{GS}

We can identify three V_{GS} ranges based on g_{DD}

g_{DD} anomalous behaviour

g_{DD} shows a non-monotonic trend at $V_{GS} \approx V_{GS,INV}$

Spatial dynamics of the SH

Gate heating:

- V_T decreases
- I_D increases
- $g_{DD,n}$ increases

SLOWER:

Most impactful at low freq.

Channel heating:

- μ degrades
- I_D decreases
- $g_{DD,n}$ decreases

FASTER:

Most impactful at high freq.

T variations in the gate are smaller and delayed compared to those in the channel

Transient simulations to validate the hypothesis

The anomaly cannot be solely ascribed to SH

Artificial degradation of the gate stack k_{th}

[E.Pop et al., JPROC 2006]
[B.Gonzalez et al., mejo 2015]

The anomaly cannot be solely ascribed to SH

Role of traps in the gDD f-dispersion

Bulk MOSFET

FDSOI MOSFET

[S.S.Islam et al., TED.2004]
[E. H. Nicollian et al., MOS physics and technology, 2002]

- Traps can cause significant dispersion of g_m and g_{DD}
- We consider bulk ($L_{CH} \approx 28\text{nm}$) and FDSOI ($L_{CH} \approx 22\text{nm}$) MOSFETs

We start investigating the role of gate stack's traps

Details on calibration and traps distribution

Bulk MOSFET

- Traps in the SiO₂ layer;
- Uniform distribution of traps in space and energy;
[M. von Haartman et al., TED 2006]
- The traps distribution is not fully quantitative → no explicit effort to fit it on the experiments

Excellent agreement with experiments

Relative importance of traps and SH

**SHEs alone
can generate
a positive**

$g_{DD,n}$

However, too
small effect to
fully explain the
experiments

**Bulk
MOSFET**

Remark:

τ_{TR} has been adjusted
via the Huang-Rhys
factor to emphasize
the separation of the
two effects in
frequency

Both traps and SH shape the g_{DD} dispersion

Interplay of traps and SH

The combination of traps and SHEs provides a credible explanation of the experiments

Traps' type influence on the g_{DD}

- Acceptor and donor trap type
- Same trap concentration

Bulk MOSFET

V_{DS} rise \rightarrow electron detrapping!

The negative charge trapped in the SiO_2 decreases; **I_D increases**

The positive charge trapped in the SiO_2 increases; **I_D increases**

The g_{DD} dispersion conveys no information on the trap type

Conclusions

- Experiments highlight a V_{GS} dependent output conductance frequency dispersion with non-monotonic frequency dependence
- The effect is qualitatively similar in all tested MOSFET technologies
- Calibrated 3D electrothermal simulations suggest that the effect cannot be ascribed to Self-Heating Effects only
- The combination of SHEs and dielectric traps provides a more convincing explanation for the experiments

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